

METHODS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' RESEARCH ACTIVITIES IN THE PROCESS OF BIOLOGY EDUCATION IN PEDAGOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: *The article shows the effectiveness of the use of various educational technologies in the development of student research activities in the process of biological education. In the coverage of research methods, it is important to develop the activities of university students through problem-solving and design technology - complexity and integration.*

Keywords: *scientific research, intellectual map, organizational, content, activity, cognitive map, task, analysis, reflection. research, research-competition, experiment, herbarium, collection, flora, fauna, volera, terrarium, aquarium*

Orientation of young people to research activities in higher education institutions around the world, training of highly qualified personnel in the field of education, their independent scientific and creative approach to each type of activity, development of competencies to apply the received innovations in practice, science, ensuring the integration of education and production, preparation for scientific and methodological activities as a competent staff is of great importance. Involvement of students in scientific work, independent research activities, the application of experimental results in practice is a solid foundation for the training of independent, potential, creative research and teaching staff.

Extensive work is being done in our country on freedom of scientific creativity, research, development and support of research activities. Development of scientific and research activities, "identification of priorities for the systematic reform of science in the future, training of highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and independent thinking, modernization of scientific infrastructure" to a qualitatively new level, pedagogical higher education Effective organization of methodological and research work in biology in educational institutions, orientation of young people in scientific organizations and higher education institutions to the systematic analysis of research work, appropriate conditions for

research activities of young scientists and students special attention is paid to the creation of [3]

In educational practice, most of the knowledge is provided ready-made and does not require additional research efforts, but the main challenge for students is to search for information independently, to acquire knowledge. Therefore, one of the most important conditions for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process is the organization of teaching and research activities of students, and its main component is the development of research skills. This not only helps students to meet the requirements of higher education qualifications, but also forms them as mature professionals, creating an internal motivation for academic activity [3]

Involvement of students in research activities, modernization and further improvement of the teaching process in the higher education system to increase motivation, increase the quality and effectiveness of teaching, independent learning through the formation of independent and creative activities of students. It is necessary to focus on research work through the proper organization and systematic organization of work in this area, to ensure continuity and to establish control and monitoring. Doing so will allow students to develop independent and creative thinking skills, broaden their scientific horizons, increase their interest in research, and focus on research[1];..

This, in turn, is a serious way to organize the work of scientific and design circles in higher education, where working with gifted students is not limited to the study and analysis of theoretical data, but also experimental. It is necessary to establish an innovative, technological approach to the development of practical measures for the implementation of experiments. To do this, special attention should be paid to the development of independent learning of students [4].

The content of research tasks is to develop students' cognitive independence, to cultivate a careful attitude to nature, to develop special learning skills, to study the diversity of flora and fauna, adaptation to the living environment, the independent study of the biology room. The resulting herbariums are intended to complement the collections [2];.

1. Learn to use research methods (teacher recommends problem-solving tasks, students solve tasks independently).

This method is based on the independent application of the acquired knowledge and skills at a high level. This method provides the experience of creative activity.

We used this method to solve creative biological tasks in the classroom.

2. Express research method. Individual assignments for empirical research include field trips and field trips:

1. What animals live in an endemic area?
2. Explain the life forms of ornamental plants in endemic areas? such as.
3. Theoretical express research should focus on independent and creative thinking.

The following research topics can be recommended: "Lifestyle of Xerophytic Plants", "Characteristics of Medicinal Plants", "Importance of Air Rooted Plants". The authors will make short presentations.

3. Conduct a learning experience. Learning experience is one of the most effective teaching methods, including practical work in biology and laboratory work. In doing so, the student will be able to work independently and gain new knowledge. In doing so, students develop the skills of analyzing data, observing, recording and recording results, drawing conclusions, and improving basic, personal, and interdisciplinary competencies.

4. Research competition. Competition is also one of the most effective methods. For example, the best "Presentation" contest. The textbook is prepared in advance. This text can be a part of the textbook: "Origin of cultivated plants and centers of diversity", "Selection of microorganisms", "Fundamentals of Genetics" and others. In composing the text of the presentation, students combine basic competencies with logical connections between specific and interdisciplinary competencies. This method teaches students to use scientific literature wisely.

5. Non-traditional lessons (presentation "Natural and artificial ecosystems", lecture "Pest control" - discussion)

Students prepare research from independent textbooks and media sources. This encourages students to be independent and creative.

6. Research projects.

In research projects, students' independent research by making plans based on a topic can be considered the highest level of research activity. By mastering the theoretical express research method, students who have the skills to do practical experimental work are successfully completing the experimental part of the projects implemented according to specially selected methods. However, one lesson is not enough to complete a study project [3].

Homework can be research:

1. The evolution of plants according to plan

Assignment: Describe the evolution of plants according to the following plan.

1. The evolution of plants on Earth

2. Unicellular and multicellular algae.
3. The growth of algae.
4. An increase in the number of joints
5. Reproduction of crustaceans
6. The development of the open seed world.
7. Closed seeds. development of the world
8. One-seeded and two-seeded class.
9. Album preparation: ("I study the animal world", "Ancient mammals")[5;]..

The use of educational technologies in the world of biology plays an important role in teaching students to think creatively and logically, in mastering the methods of intellectual activity, in developing their scientific, critical-analytical, logical thinking skills and in directing research activities.

Thus, in the process of teaching biology, students use a variety of methods, forms and tools to develop research activities. At the same time, in the process of teaching biology, the technology of developing students' research activities also plays an important role in providing them with sufficient experience in this field.

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